

Tourism Competitiveness Strategy in Indonesia through Strengthening Human Resources Education in Tourism Post Pandemic

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Abstract:- This paper reviews specific policies on human resources in the tourism sector in the short and medium term based on the role of science and education based on research and data. There are 60 literature reviews on the portrait of tourism before and after the Covid-19 pandemic, including policies issued by the Indonesian government at this time. The findings recommend that local government reform and review tourism development planning, emphasize Resilience, Adaptation, Transformation, Sustainable Tourism, human resource guidance, and strengthen the quality and quantity of tourism demand and supply. Furthermore, the government needs to continue to improve the Pentahelix collaboration strategy, especially with tourism institutions that play a role in shaping human resources, so that they are more optimal in tourism development in the new normal era.

Keywords:- Resilience, Adaptation, Transformation, Sustainable Tourism, Human Resources, Education, Covid-19.

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 outbreak has brought up serious health risks all over the world. This pandemic outbreak is among the most infectious in recent history. According to WHO, this virus had spread to 232 countries as of June 25, 2022, with 539,893,858 cases and 6,324,112 deaths (covid19.go.id). Due to the rapid transmission of the newer version of the coronavirus, which also continues to mutate, authorities worldwide are forced to start imposing lockdowns. The spread of the virus has seriously threatened life, and measures such as lockdowns have put people's livelihoods at risk (Sharma & Mahendru, 2020). Some industries have been able to adapt to digital platforms and continue their survival struggle, but others have not (Mehroliya, Alagarsamy, & Solaikutty, 2020).

The decline in the number of travelers in Indonesia has a meaningful direct and indirect economic impact on the tourism industry. The drop in tourist numbers by 22% in the first quarter of 2020, and a drop of 60% to 80% overall in 2020, are some warning signs of a global crisis that could result in the bankruptcy of the global tourism industry. During the Covid-19 pandemic, the occupancy rate of star hotels in Indonesia fell dramatically. In 2020, the percentage of star hotels in Jakarta fell by 36%, Bali by 73.8%, Yogyakarta by 41.2%, and Indonesia as a whole fell by 39.8%. (Paludi, 2022). Based on the WTTC, travel and

tourism support up to 100 million jobs. According to Nurjaman et al. (2020), economic activities in industries other than tourism, heavily reliant on human resources, are rare. As a result, human resources are the most critical aspect of tourism, as they directly impact the tourism market's competitiveness and viability (Mubarok et al., 2020).

The hotel industry no longer maintains its human resources in Ghana due to a lack of government policies and support for tourism industry players, including hotel employees (Dwomoh et al., 2020). The perception of a career in the tourism industry certainly has a significant effect on all students in higher education, who must be more prepared and equipped to succeed in this highly vulnerable industry. According to (Reichenberger & Raymond, 2021), changes to this pandemic should be positively designed to find temporary work during the early recovery period.

Indonesia's Ministry of Tourism (Kemenparekraf) has designed three recovery phases, namely Emergency Response, Recovery, and Normalization, which have been socially constructed under the name 'new normal era' as a short and medium-term strategy for the tourism sector stakeholders. Tourism players must have extraordinary capabilities to stay in business, such as concern for health, security, and safety and increasing new capabilities through digitalization. Previous research on Covid-19 that impacts the tourism sector has emerged to find solutions and develop strategies for regional tourism recovery in the new normal era; scientists and academics must conduct research and collect empirical data. This research will examine several studies on the subject.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Crisis

Tourism is prone to crises (Dolnicar & Zare, 2020; Gössling et al., 2020). Over the years, many destinations have been affected by natural and artificial crises, leading to the development of various resilience and mitigation tactics and strategies (Ritchie & Jiang, 2019). However, the crisis caused by the Covid-19 pandemic is distinct in many ways. Travel bans, hotel closures, and tourism halts have resulted from a massive global economic disaster that has the potential to result in fundamental changes in many segments of tourism (Dolnicar & Zare, 2020), and the worst part is that the end of this crisis is uncertain.

A review of the current literature on Covid-19 and its impact on the tourism industry reveals that most of the texts published thus far are opinion papers or research notes. Only a few papers have been written using empirical methods, such as Yang et al., 2020 and Gössling et al., 2020. However, no single strategy is suitable for all regions because the pandemic's implications depend entirely on each region's character (Head, 2007).

B. Resilience

The ability of a group or society to cope with external pressures and disturbances arising from social, political, and environmental dynamics so that they can recover from an event that causes setbacks or difficulties, even grow and become resilient, adaptation to these events, is referred to as resilience. Luthans et al., 2006 in Ramdhani and Kiswanto, 2020; Maliati and Chalid, 2021). Resilience can also assess a system's ability to absorb and recover from dangerous events (Mayunga in Irwanto et al., 2021). Although supporting resilience in an organization requires a highly skilled workforce (Dessouky & Al-Ghareeb, 2020), increasing understanding and use of technology is critical for the world of tourism to survive business in the pandemic era (Kumar, 2021).

C. New Normal Era

The new normal era is characterized by new regulations and a scenario emphasizing health as the primary indicator in people's lives; A Certified Healthcare Simulation Educator implements this to accelerate social and economic recovery following COVID-19. In addition, the tourism sector's enormous impact on the well-being of people, places, and the country's economy requires us to adapt to the post-pandemic so that this sector is more resilient and operationally fair (Benjamin et al., 2020).

Various remedies and solutions accompany the implementation of this new normal to improve and develop the tourism industry for it to survive in the event of a pandemic in the future. The tourism sector's adaptation to a pandemic situation is related to tourism activities that have ceased due to various social constraints (Svagzdiene et al., 2020).

D. Adaptation

Individuals and communities use the adaptive capacity to create and implement decisions that allow them to manage risks posed by changes in perceived or projected internal and external conditions (Eakin & Luers, 2006; Füssel, 2007; Smit & Pilifosova, 2001). Individuals react differently to various environmental stimuli or conditions (Wohlwill, 1974). A human adaptation strategy is a pattern of behaviour or action planned to meet basic needs and solve problems (Putra, 2003).

This method is an act of duplication or coping, representing a person's or group's ability to apply a set of imitation methods to overcome various life problems through planned efforts or actions to meet the expected needs (Suharto, 2009). For example, during the Covid-19 pandemic, three aspects were adopted: 1) cultural adaptation (for example, work culture, organizational

culture, and community culture have changed); 2) social adaptation (many people help decrease talking and physical contact); and 3) economic adaptation (globally, this situation has not yet received the appropriate strategy, but one of the adaptive responses in digital economic transactions is beginning to become one of the solutions).

E. Transformation

Following the formulation of various resilience efforts, tourism transformed from Mass Tourism to Digital Tourism. This transformation into Digital Tourism makes use of technology. Technology is a fundamental need to support activities in this era of globalization. Moreover, given the pandemic that has limited mobility for potential tourists, the presence of technology is becoming increasingly important (Yasintha, 2022).

The digital transformation of supply and demand management must also be maintained (Montanari, 2020). Furthermore, many changes following the pandemic will be driven by new technologies that can usher in a new era of cyber tourism and virtual tourism, defined as a combination of natural and virtual hybrid tourism. According to Brouder (2020), the presence of COVID-19 has successfully pushed the tourism industry to unleash its transformative potential by restoring and evolving forward. The demand side of tourists adjusts their behavior by creating new tourism norms that are more locally oriented, friendly to nature (eco-tourism), sustainable tourism, and more.

F. Sustainable Tourism

According to Swarbrooke (1999) in Kristiana et al. (2021), there are three types of sustainable tourism development: environmental, economic, and social. Nature, agriculture, and community development comprise the environmental dimension. Cater (1993) and Lemy et al. (2019) identify three main goals of sustainable tourism: (1) to meet the needs of local communities to improve their standard of living in the short and long term; (2) to meet tourist demand; and (3) to protect the natural environment from achieving the last two objectives.

Sustainable tourism is derived from sustainable development, prioritizing preserving natural and cultural resources so that future generations can enjoy them (Candranegara et al., 2021). Because the tourism industry will undoubtedly be reorganized based on actual planning rather than documents following COVID-19, now is the best time to promote a sustainable and equitable tourism industry (Benjamin et al., 2020). Industry must prioritize education, environmental and social justice, and racial healing. Sustainability is a continuous procedure for achieving positive outcomes that involve changing public beliefs, desires, information, skills, and awareness (Galvani et al., 2020). Expert knowledge and experience must be put into practice to shift to sustainable tourism (Chang et al., 2020; Prideaux et al., 2020).

G. Education in Tourism

Kunwar (2018) states that tourism is a characteristic activity of the contemporary era, and tourism education is believed to be the backbone of supporting the industry. In general, the provision of tourism education follows trends in the industry, such as in Indonesia, which has the HILDIKTIPARI institution as an Indonesian higher education institutional organization. With the expansion of tourism activities, the education system is responsible for preparing a skilled and qualified workforce who can provide quality services in the industry (Gu et al., 2007). The new requirements for human capital in modern conditions on highly qualified specialists consider the development of an up-to-date policy of increasing the competitiveness level of national human resources as the state for balancing the labour market, achieving economic growth, and ensuring the quality of the population's life. In this regard, education and skills are critical to promoting growth and providing employment. Moreover, a region's high levels of human capital can benefit local employment levels due to production- or consumption-related mechanisms (or both) (Tiwari et al., 2021).

III. METHODOLOGY RESEARCH

This study uses a design with the Literature review method that identifies, assesses, and interprets all findings on a research topic. A study is a research conducted by collecting several books and scientific research articles related to the problem and purpose of the research, which in this case is related to the Covid-19 pandemic situation, which limits researchers in data collection. This technique is carried out to reveal various theories relevant to the problems faced and investigated as reference material in discussing research results.

Sources are obtained from national and international journals using the Google Scholar portal by typing five keywords in the title. Use this database to obtain quality and reputable article standards. The keywords used are "Covid-19", "new normal era", "human resources", "tourism", "sustainable tourism", and "education", the authors found 81 papers. These papers were then filtered by looking at the titles and abstracts; then, it was found that 60 papers were by the themes studied, while the remaining 21 were not used. The following 60 selected papers were further analyzed; the cluster grouping of these papers is shown in the following table:

No	Keyword	Cluster
1	Impact Covid-19	Post-pandemic tourism challenges
2	Post Pandemic	
3	New Normal Era	
4	Adaptation post-pandemic	
5	Transformation post-pandemic	
6	Destination	Post-pandemic tourism resilience
7	Sustainable tourism	
8	Business Sustainability	
9	Tourism development	
10	Research and data	
11	Science and Education	
12	Resilience	
13	Digitization	Tourism transformation and adaptation
14	Future tourism	
15	HR Strategies	
16	Megatrends tourism	
17	Supply and demand	
18	e-tourism	
19	Human Development	Education
20	Online Learning and Teaching	
21	Curriculum Transformation	
22	Industry Collaboration	
23	Experiential Education	

Table 1: Cluster Literature Data Review of the Study

- Research Question
 - RQ1. What problems or issues were found in human resources in the tourism industry during the COVID-19 pandemic?
 - RQ2. What strategies can be used to recover human resources in the tourism industry after COVID-19?

IV. DISCUSSION

The COVID-19 pandemic has severely hit the tourism and hospitality industry worldwide. Based on a review of 30 papers studying the tourism industry during the pandemic and post-pandemic, the authors propose a research-based framework and data generated from the development of science and human education to revive the post-COVID-19 regional tourism industry. This framework was built based on the results of research worldwide that describe the seven main factors to build the resilience of the regional tourism industry in the New Normal Era. Namely government regulation, adaptation, transformation, local ownership, tourism industry trust, sustainable tourism, and education. As people face an unprecedented pandemic, it is past time to assess the status of nationally funded projects in developed countries to develop international collaborative research strategies from an interdisciplinary standpoint (Lee., Kang., and Kim, 2020).

A. *Tourism Industry Resilience in Indonesia*

One example of the concept of organizational resilience we can learn from the Government of Gianyar Regency, Bali, in dealing with the Covid-19 pandemic is not only seen in how quickly the community can rise from the impact of the pandemic but also in the ability to cope, learn, and adapt during the pandemic. Therefore, organizational resilience must be organized as optimally as possible so that the effects of disasters can quickly pass through the recovery process. The measurement of resilience relates to collecting and analyzing data through opportunities that the implementer may carry out to see the variables' dynamic correlation. Studies on resilience are needed to describe the heterogeneity of welfare that is temporary or permanent from an event that has received an external threat. The threat referred to in this study is the Covid-19 pandemic.

The business world recognizes resilience as a crisis management tool/strategy for business stability and adaptability to all risks during natural disasters and emergencies. Furthermore, business resilience is related to the organization's ability to adapt to new environments and circumstances to reduce the impact of these incidents (Supardi., Kudus., Hadi, 2020). Resilience strategies require coordination, various crisis management techniques, good relations (between all stakeholders), comprehensive networks, recognition of risks and opportunities, and timely and measurable interventions (Alves, Lok, Luo, & Hao, 2020; Fitriasisari, 2020). The literature on resilience identifies resilience attributes that are proactive, absorptive/adaptive, reactive, or dynamic (Supardi et al., 2020). Historically, tourism has quickly bounced back after disasters, pandemics, and epidemics such as Ebola, Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS), and severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS). Local, regional, or national governments assist the industry's recovery by attracting investors through tax breaks, lenient land use rules, and others. (Brouder, 2020; Ioannides & Gyimothy, 2020). Before international travel can resume, domestic tourism will encourage the resumption of the tourism industry after the pandemic. Other factors, including technology resilience, local ownership, and customer and employee trust, can help build industry resilience, which is necessary today.

The paralysis of tourism nationally and globally due to the lockdown policies in various countries and the Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) policy in Indonesia affects the operations of the tourism business. It raises deep concerns for Tourism HR about the future of the tourism business. Research conducted by Simanjuntak and Fitriana (2020) discusses cultural shock, adaptation, and self-concept of tourism human resources in welcoming the new normal era from a communication perspective, both related to intercultural communication, interpersonal communication, and self-concept as part of communication psychology. The results showed that tourism HR experienced culture shock and reached its lowest point from March to mid-April but increased slowly from late April to June. According to BPS 2020 data, approximately 409,000 tourism workers have lost their jobs due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Wuryandani (2020) also stated that the reduction in working hours

reflected a decrease in the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the Indonesian tourism sector. Working hours were reduced for approximately 12.91 million people in the tourism sector, and 939 thousand people were temporarily laid off. On the other hand, the COVID-19 pandemic has a direct impact on a variety of tourism-related jobs.

Three aspects of life significantly suppress the tourism industry: cultural, social, and economic. The cultural and social aspects are relatively easy to overcome, but the economic aspect has the most impact because it involves their survival and their families. The awareness period in the adaptation process is a time of struggle, creativity, and action, so many of them switch professions to run online businesses. This period is still ongoing, and it is unknown how long it will last. A positive self-concept plays an essential role in a person's success in adapting to survive because it helps a person be tough, patient, courageous, and creative in finding solutions to challenges to open up more significant opportunities to solve problems successfully. Of the various problems that arise in the community, it is deemed necessary to provide a form of community empowerment practice through increased knowledge and education. The main goal is not only to solve problems related to economic income but also to make people the ability to meet their physical, economic, and social needs. The practice of community empowerment is not only understood as a change activity carried out from within the individual, community, or organization but also requires support and encouragement from outside parties. One of the many institutions that play a role in implementing community empowerment practices is Higher Education, either directly or indirectly through the implementation of the Tridharma of Higher Education. However, in its implementation, the role of universities in community empowerment, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic, is not as simple as imagined. Although there are opportunities to implement it, there are also challenges that universities will face. Therefore, at least a strategic policy step is needed from the central government to strengthen the role of Higher Education in the Covid-19 Pandemic Period (Saleh., Mujahiddin, 2020).

B. *Transformation of Tourism Education in Human Development*

Humanity's struggle against the Covid-19 pandemic has forced scientists and governments to seek new methods and technologies so that all schools, universities, industries, and hospitals can operate adequately. One of the first policies taken by governments in various countries is the lockdown, while Indonesia enforces a policy of social restrictions in public spaces through several stages. This policy is detrimental to the economy, so various solutions have emerged so that all work and school activities can continue to run. One of the leading solutions is to work and study from home, which is to conduct meetings through cyberspace with internet media. Academics have taken root in technology as the leading solution for resilience to the impact of COVID-19 on the hospitality and tourism industry. Several studies have thoroughly explored this technology for the industry (Osei., Ragavan., Mensah., Kandappan, 2020). Various technological innovations and

applications have been developed to fight the coronavirus pandemic. However, the pandemic also has implications for technology's design, development, and use. Therefore, there is an urgent need for a greater understanding of what role information systems and technology researchers can play in this global pandemic. New technologies used to reduce the threat of COVID-19 and the relevant challenges associated with the design, development, and use of technology, provide insight and advice on how information systems and technology scientists can help combat the COVID-19 pandemic (He., Zhang., Li, 2020).

Digital technology is forced to carry out various innovations in a short and fast time, so scientists are competing to make discoveries and research. Technology related to 5G and the Internet of Things (IoT) can be efficiently utilized and developed to combat the COVID-19 pandemic. Some cases on 5G and IoT can deliver innovative telehealth solutions, contact tracing, education, retail, and supply chain, e-government/remote office/information sharing, intelligent manufacturing, and factory automation, e-tourism, and entertainment presented with its technical requirements and challenges. It is estimated that the proposed solution will play a role in facilitating lifestyle, work, and other daily human activities in the post-pandemic world (Siriwardhana et al., 2020). To realize this potential, e-Tourism research needs to challenge the existing paradigm and critically evaluate its ontological and epistemological foundations. Given the importance of rethinking the paradigms of contemporary science, growth, and technology, the researchers present six pillars to guide scientists in efforts to transform e-Tourism through their research, including historicity, reflexivity, equity, transparency, plurality, and creativity to embrace transformative research (Gretzel et al., 2020).

C. Sustainable Human Resources in Tourism

Many studies have found that Covid-19 has destroyed various aspects of human life. However, many scientists also argue that the pandemic positively impacts reforming the tourism industry to be more ethical, responsible, and sustainable. The debates and discussions on the TriNet Tourism Information Network also discussed the struggles of tourism academics in the proper role. The results of this debate impact the development of the discipline, education of tourism students, and the future of tourism practice after the pandemic (Desbiolles, 2021). Based on a recent review of the crisis recovery process, the tourism sector is likely to recover from this sudden market shock, mainly due to various forms of government intervention.

Nevertheless, while policymakers seek to strengthen tourism resilience post-pandemic, subsidies and other initiatives serve to maintain a fundamentally flawed market logic. Therefore, the crisis has given us the perfect opportunity to choose a new direction and move forward by adopting a more sustainable path. In particular, COVID-19 offers public, private, and academic actors a unique opportunity to design and consolidate the transition to greener and more balanced tourism. Academics can lead in this by redesigning curricula based on research and data to prepare future industry leaders with knowledge and

education to pursue more responsible tourism (Ioannides., Gyimóthy (2020). In addition, various research results suggest ways to -way forward that are not limited to adopting an innovative way of life, doing business, reassessing our relationship with nature, increasing spending on education, and tax exemptions (Iwuoha, 2020).

The revival and development of regional tourism after the Covid-19 pandemic will appear more quickly (Ida et al., 2020) because people tend to release their fatigue by traveling domestically for health security. On the other hand, Covid-19 has changed the world in every way, including changes in tourist demand (Chang et al., 2020), because they have their perceptions of the risk of Covid-19 (Tasci & Sönmez, 2019). Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the tourism market from the demand side of its characteristics, typology, behavior, and preferences (Chakravarty et al., 2021; Ivanova et al., 2021; Li et al., 2021; Putra et al., 2020). This study helps determine strategies for attracting tourists in the new normal era, maximizing tourist satisfaction with tourism destinations, determining prices, and developing tourism products according to tourist characteristics (Paramita & Putra, 2020; Saway et al., 2021).

Tourist behavior in the new normal period prioritizes safe travel, where tourists consider outdoor tourism to have minimal risk of the possibility of transmitting the Covid-19 virus. It is in line with Lebrun et al. (2021) that the experience of domestic tourists in protected natural areas has become a travel trend during the pandemic.

Tourism Adaptation Post-Covid-19 Pandemic has transformed the tourism market shaped by consumer demand and, in turn, shaped megatrends and short-term consumer trends. Euromonitor International's Megatrends framework illustrates the significant impact of changes affecting the wider industry. The pattern of tourism behavior of domestic tourists concerning post-pandemic tourism shows a trend that tourists, who are millennial and millennial, are very concerned about cleanliness, health, security, and environmental sustainability. Tourism stakeholders need to make natural tourist attractions a primary attraction with cultural and artificial tourism attractions supporting tourist attractions and preparing their communities for post-pandemic destination management. It is to realize safe travel for tourists as a step to restoring tourist visits in Indonesia (Harianja et al., 2022). Understanding of changing tourism trends must be studied more deeply for tourism providers to be able to provide services, both services, and products. The role of academics is to help students who are prepared later to understand this changing trend so that they can apply safe travel for both tourists and environmental sustainability for tourism in the future. The long-term consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic are likely to trigger more permanent changes related to the digitization of jobs and activities. Other daily activities, thereby reducing mobility requirements and overall fossil energy consumption. The crisis prompted the government system to be better prepared for the future, posing the threat of an increasingly populist or democratic political response and increased securitization. These

developments can guide research by addressing the reproduction of new practices emerging from the COVID-19 outbreak to accelerate the sustainability transition, increase understanding of the role of governance in transitions, and pay attention to the ethical and political implications of landscape shocks.

Co-creating quality models or prototypes can develop sustainable tourism. Sustainable tourism prioritizes system updates, standards, synergies, a capacity scale for improving the quality of tourism products and markets, niche tourism (specialized tourism), and increasing integration and ecosystem management and government. So that reformulation is obtained to improve regulations, investment, marketing, human resources, and various science-based public research or knowledge-based tourism. Sustainable Tourism Development can help the continuity of the tourism industry after Covid-19 because one of the places that underlie Sustainable Tourism is a tourist destination that is not too crowded. Considering the argument and the existing regulations regarding lockdown and social distancing rules, the practice of Sustainable Tourism can be a potential solution to stimulate the movement of tourists and help the revival of the tourism industry. Regional tourism management must have a business strategy to maintain the continuity of the tourism business after the COVID-19 pandemic by empowering the role of Penta Helix. Based on the Indonesian government's strategy to strengthen human resources in tourism, three crucial things form the basis for the tourism industry's recovery.

- It is the optimization of institutions and curricula for tourism and creative economy vocational education and training. In Indonesia, there is a significant and growing skills mismatch between industry demands and the capabilities of vocational and higher education graduates. A comprehensive understanding must include research on various tourism-related policy, planning, and development topics, as well as the development of educational technology. More importantly, developing attitudes toward future challenges and coping with international standards on the one hand and the local cultural context on the other is the key to improving human resources in the tourism industry. Mursid et al. (2022) support this by stating that a project-based blended learning program and creative thinking skills in vocational schools will increase student learning outcomes. It is hoped that superior and competitive tourism and creative economy human resources will be produced.
- It is improving the competency certification of human tourism resources and the creative economy. Certification is required to ensure that the workforce can compete with workers from other countries regarding competence and quality. The goal is to create equity in increasing human resources in Indonesia's tourism industry, both in education and for tourism workers. The provisions of Number reinforce this: SE: 011/BNPSP/IV/2020 April 03, 2020. which allows remote competency assessments/tests carried out by LSP to support government strategies in the health and safety agenda. It can produce good outputs

with its technical skills, namely the achievement of targets and work programs that can be implemented.

- It is strengthening tourism and creative economy communities and institutions. The creative economy can be used as one solution for societal welfare because the creative economy system adds value to either the industry or its human resources. The presence of a creative economy has a positive impact on lowering unemployment and raising the level of the economy. The management of communities and community institutions in the fields of tourism and the creative economy will be able to significantly, evenly, and thoroughly encourage the growth of these fields.

The government policies above are reviewed to determine the policies taken in rebuilding the tourism sector to welcome the new normal era. As the holder of control over every decision for regulations implemented in every line, the government plays an important role, particularly in mitigation policies and defense against Covid-19 for the tourism industry. The government must measure the resilience of each industry. Understand the broad pattern, and identify problems that arise so that later decisions can be made after simplifying information and the most recent information related to the problems encountered in achieving the government's goals, particularly in the tourism industry. By examining various phenomena, challenges, and potentials, referring to relevant references. The results of a descriptive literature review on government policies taken in developing the tourism sector by putting forward a social safety net (safety, security, healthy) in the opening of the tourism sector. In the policy in developing the tourism sector, three aspects must exist, namely; Sustenance (the ability to maintain the existence of a destination), Self Esteem (inviting the community to be involved in managing tourism), and freedom from servitude (granting regional freedom in managing tourism). The government encourages in-city tourism, or in-city tourism (Azizi, A. W., Larasati, E., & Yuniningsih, 2021). As a result of all existing studies, the best strategy for regionally strengthening tourism for each region in Indonesia can be developed with the support of all tourism stakeholders, and universities will play an essential role in future tourism. They are starting with concept renewal, sustainable tourism development, and human resources preparation to run the entire tourism field. Having quality human resources and the appropriate number of people to run the tourism industry in the new normal era will instill confidence in tourists and help to restore domestic and foreign tourism in all tourist destinations.

V. CONCLUSION

The tourism industry is one of the areas most affected by the Coronavirus. People cannot take vacations due to a slew of travel restrictions, so the tourism industry is paralyzed. It impacts all human resources in tourism, as they cannot perform their daily duties and may be forced to seek alternative employment to support themselves and their families. Of course, the Indonesian government faces a significant challenge in identifying the opportunities and threats it will encounter in the tourism sector following

COVID-19. Finally, the government has issued a new order system known as the new normal. Several strategies are implemented as part of this new normal, beginning with transforming and adapting universities' learning systems and curricula. Understanding and improving technology skills is the primary foundation for all human resources in adapting to COVID-19, particularly in the study of technology. Furthermore, all tourism stakeholders contribute to this, beginning with government policies, the development of the concept of sustainable tourism, the preparation of quality human resources, and acceptance support from tourism industry players. As a solution for the Indonesian government to rise in the post-pandemic era, the Pentahalix strategy is the key to fulfilling the competitiveness of human tourism resources.

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